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Fasciola hepatica induces Foxp3 T cell, proinflammatory and regulatory cytokine overexpression in liver from infected sheep during early stages of infection

Isabel L. Pacheco¹, Nieves Abril², Rafael Zafra³, Verónica Molina-Hernández¹, Noelia Morales-Prieto², María J. Bautista¹, María T. Ruiz-Campillo¹, Raúl Pérez-Caballero³, Alvaro Martínez-Moreno³ and José Pérez^{1*}

Abstract

The expression of T regulatory cells (Foxp3), regulatory (interleukin [IL]-10 and transforming growth factor beta [TGF- β]) and proinflammatory (tumor necrosis factor alpha [TNF- α] and interleukin [IL]-1 β) cytokines was quantified using real time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR) in the liver of sheep during early stages of infection with *Fasciola hepatica* (1, 3, 9, and 18 days post-infection [dpi]). Portal fibrosis was also evaluated by Masson's trichrome stain as well as the number of Foxp3⁺ cells by immunohistochemistry. Animals were divided into three groups: (a) group 1 was immunized with recombinant cathepsin L1 from *F. hepatica* (FhCL1) in Montanide adjuvant and infected; (b) group 2 was uniquely infected with *F. hepatica*; and (c) group 3 was the control group, unimmunized and uninfected. An overexpression of regulatory cytokines of groups 1 and 2 was found in all time points tested in comparison with group 3, particularly at 18 dpi. A significant increase of the number of Foxp3⁺ lymphocytes in groups 1 and 2 was found at 9 and 18 dpi relative to group 3. A progressive increase in portal fibrosis was found in groups 1 and 2 in comparison with group 3. In this regard, group 1 showed smaller areas of fibrosis than group 2. There was a significant positive correlation between Foxp3 and IL-10 expression (by immunohistochemistry and qRT-PCR) just as between portal fibrosis and TGF- β gene expression. The expression of proinflammatory cytokines increased gradually during the experience. These findings suggest the induction of a regulatory phenotype by the parasite that would allow its survival at early stages of the disease when it is more vulnerable.

Introduction

Fasciolosis, caused by *Fasciola hepatica*, produces high economic losses to the agricultural sector [1]. This parasite infects a wide range of domestic animals including cattle, sheep, and goats, and the disease has been recognized as an important zoonosis in Africa, Asia, Europe, America, and Oceania [2, 3]. Traditionally, the control of the disease has been based on the use of anthelmintic drugs. Nevertheless, resistance to triclabendazole

and other drugs as well as the public concern about the presence of drug metabolites in foodstuff is increasing in numerous countries [4]. Due to this, during the last few years an enormous interest in the development of an immunological method to control the disease has risen [5, 6]. Despite major efforts during the last two decades, the search for an effective vaccine to control this disease has been slow. This is due to the different mechanisms used by *F. hepatica* to modulate the host immune response making it ineffective to kill the parasites [7–9]. One of these mechanisms, like for other helminths, is the expansion of T regulatory cells (Foxp3), facilitating both parasite survival and modulation of tissue damage [10, 11]. Our group has recently shown the expansion of

*Correspondence: an1pearj@uco.es

¹ Department of Anatomy and Comparative Pathology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Córdoba, Sanidad Animal Building, Rabanales Campus, Córdoba, Spain

Full list of author information is available at the end of the article

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